

Free-electron infrared nonlinearities in heavily doped InGaAs nanoantennas

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Abstract—Free electrons in heavily doped semiconductors operate in the hydrodynamic regime, where oscillating velocity, current and electromagnetic field terms can mix and produce relatively strong nonlinear effects in the mid-infrared and terahertz ranges. We fabricate n-InGaAs nanoantennas with the aim of measuring the efficiency of third harmonic generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

HYDRODYNAMIC models of free electrons in metals and in degenerately doped semiconductors can describe accurately a range of nanoscale plasmonic phenomena that occur at interfaces, nanoantennas, metasurfaces. In fact, considering the nonlocal response of a free electron liquid can be more relevant (and computationally much less expensive) than including the correct band-orbital description of the solid. As every hydrodynamic model, second- and third-order nonlinear terms arise as a natural consequence of nonlocality and mixing of velocity, current and force (field) terms in the equations of motion and in the Maxwell's equations. This free electron nonlinearity can be rather strong if compared to the natural nonlinearity of the host crystal. In particular, the nonlinear terms are inversely proportional to the effective mass and to the electron density ($N \sim 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), pointing towards heavily doped semiconductors as the ideal systems to observe such nonlinear effects, although this requires operation at infrared frequencies below the plasma frequency [1, 2]. We are exploring the possibility of exploiting this nonlinearity in forthcoming photonic integrated circuits operating at mid-infrared wavelengths.

In the project NEHO we are focusing on epitaxial N-type doped InGaAs layers ($m^* = 0.07m_e$) grown on insulating InP substrates. Apart from the free carrier absorption, these materials can be considered as transparent in the mid-infrared (wavelengths of 14 to 3 μm at least) and are therefore suitable for designing integrated waveguides. Nonlinear interaction sections can be designed by adding a doped InGaAs layer to specific sections of the waveguides, where the hydrodynamic interactions will take place. However, to quantify the third-order nonlinearity and test our hydrodynamic model, we started from the fabrication of nanoantenna arrays [3] and the measurement of the third harmonic generation (THG) with ultrashort-pulse mid-IR laser sources [4]. Three doping levels have been explored: $6 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $9 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and $1.1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, corresponding to plasma wavelengths of 9.6, 8.0 and 7.3 μm respectively, as determined by FTIR reflectance spectroscopy

Fig. 1. (a) Sectional view of the n-InGaAs nanoantennas on InP substrate with a range of dimensions of the fabricated devices. (b) Scanning electron micrographs of the antennas fabricated by e-beam lithography and deep reactive ion etching. (c) Numerical simulations of the linear extinction spectrum of the same antenna on differently doped InGaAs epitaxial layers. Note the scaling of the resonances with the plasma frequency of the semiconductor. (d) FTIR reflectance measurements of the corresponding antenna arrays (dipole antenna length: 2.2 μm , width: 0.5 μm), with good correspondence to simulations in (c). Curves are vertically offset in (d), the pink curve corresponds to antennas fabricated in the undoped layer.

on the as-grown material. Undoped InGaAs layers have been also grown and are used as reference to measure the crystal nonlinearity.

II. RESULTS

Starting from the fundamental equation of the hydrodynamic model in the limit of Thomas-Fermi approximation, following a perturbative approach and expanding all the fields up to the third order, we derive an equation to describe the polarization field $P(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and, as a consequence, the nonlinear response of heavily doped semiconductors under the influence of external electric and magnetic fields can be obtained from what can be considered a nonlocal version of the conventional Drude model. This response is used in numerical simulations to predict the THG efficiency of nanoantennas.

In Figure 1 we report the antenna design (a), the electron microscopy images (b), the linear extinction simulations for the

three different doping levels (c), and the linear reflectance spectra measured by FTIR. The overall agreement between (c) and (d) confirms the good quality of the fabrication and simulations processes.

Nonlinear THG efficiency measurement with ultrashort-pulse mid-IR laser sources is ongoing, with measurements techniques based on difference-frequency generation in nonlinear crystals to produce high-power mid-infrared pulses, similar to those previously employed to determine THG efficiency in N-doped germanium nanoantennas [4].

III. SUMMARY

We are exploring free electron nonlinearities in the hydrodynamic regime in heavily doped InGaAs epitaxial layers with small electron effective mass, to be used in future integrated photonics applications. Hydrodynamic effects are expected to provide relatively high and tunable nonlinear efficiency if compared to crystal nonlinearities. Nonlinear mid-infrared measurements on nanoantenna arrays are ongoing.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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